

TECHNICAL, CONSTRUCTIVE SAFETY OF CHILDREN'S TOYS AND ASPECTS OF INFLUENCING ON CHILDREN'S CONSCIOUSNESS

Kenjayeva Zarifa Suyunovna

Tashkent State Technical University

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Abstract. *Children's toys play an important role in understanding the world, expanding the world of imagination and building the vocabulary of our little boys and girls. According to the data, more than 3 billion toys are produced and sold annually in the world. Unfortunately, about 60 percent of the toys sold on the world market are not quality controlled.*

Children's toys must be designed and manufactured in such a way that they do not pose a threat to the health and life of children and their dependents.

Keywords: *children's toys, vocabulary, wood, rubber, plastic.*

According to the current regulations, any type of children's toy imported into the territory of Uzbekistan must have a certificate of conformity, a document confirming that it meets the specified requirements. They are also required to have a hygienic certificate. However, it is impossible to ignore the fact that at the market stalls where toys are sold, there are also low-quality dolls and toys that do not correspond to our national mentality, have a negative effect on children's health and psyche, do not meet sanitary and hygienic requirements. The fact that these are mostly toys brought to our country from abroad through roundabout ways and have not passed the control of relevant organizations encourages us to be more vigilant.

Children's toys that are not intended for children under three years of age are made of wood, rubber, cardboard, metal, glass, fabric, cotton, leather, porcelain, as well as polymer. A toy made of polymer compounds is light, elastic, beautiful, durable. Due to its smoothness, it is less dirty and easy to clean. However, it is possible that polymers release harmful chemical compounds into the child's mouth during slurping and have a negative effect on the child's health.

When using toys, it is necessary that the chemicals contained in them do not harm the user's health as a result of falling into the respiratory tract, skin, eyes and mucous membrane of the stomach.

Chemical toys and play sets that are not used for chemical experiments are allowed to contain certain amounts of substances or reagents, provided that they do not exceed the maximum permitted amount for each substance.

A children's toy must be designed and manufactured in such a way that it does not pose a threat to the health and life of children and their dependents. The following are recommended for the technical and structural safety of children's toys:

- The raw materials used in the production of children's toys must be clean (non-polluted), not related to infectious diseases and technically comply with the requirements of regulatory documents in the field of regulation.

- Use of natural fur, natural leather, glass, porcelain, painted rubber, cardboard and paper, objects that increase in size by more than 5% in a wet environment, and granules of 3 mm or less in filling toys for children under 3 years of age is not allowed.

- It is not allowed to use secondary raw materials for children's toys, that is, raw materials used for other purposes and obtained from processing. It is allowed to use the waste of one's own enterprise in the production of children's toys.

- The protective-decorative surface coating of children's toys should be resistant to moisture, saliva and sweat.

- Children's toys must be designed and manufactured in such a way that they do not endanger the life and health of children and persons supervising them when used in accordance with their purpose.

- Physical and mechanical characteristics of children's toys. Children's toy and its components and their connecting parts must be resistant to mechanical stress, not be damaged, and not lose their consumer properties when they are used according to their intended purpose..

- The edges, sharp points, hard parts, springs, fasteners, spacers, corners, bends, electrical cords, ropes and fasteners of children's toy must not pose a risk of injury to children. The exposed edges of the toys must not be sharp or sharpened, there must be no cracks, and the fixed parts of the bolt and screw threads must be covered with a protective coating with a thread length of more than 3 mm and a depth of not less than 0.5 mm. Constructors are excluded.

- Children's toys made of wood must not have knots or places where worms have fallen.

- The moving parts of children's toy must not pose a risk of injury to the child. Actuators must be covered with covers.

- The front wheel of two-wheeled children's toys must be able to turn $90^\circ \pm 5^\circ$ in both directions relative to the straight line of travel.

- Toys intended for children under 3 years of age that attach directly to food and their detachable parts must be of such a size that they do not pose a risk of falling into the child's upper respiratory tract.

- Children's toys with a mechanical or electric transmission, a freewheel mechanism or a neutral position of the gearbox must have a braking device. Children's toys that carry children's weight and whose wheels are driven by the child's hand or foot, or equipped with electric drive through a mechanical transmission, are allowed to be manufactured without braking devices. Children's toys with a chain drive must be equipped with a protective cover. Anti-slip elements must be installed on the base surface.

Children's intellectual potential and development is formed by the influence of the environment. Nowadays, it is customary for children to spend most of their time with toys, so the psychological impact of toys is very important for human development. Recommendations on the impact of toys on psychology:

- Animals in the form of giant creatures, in the form of robots. Such toys, designed to play "war", awaken an aggressive spirit in the child.

- Fluffy woolen toys: the fur of teddy bears and rabbits can get into the child's mouth, itch, cause allergies. And the eye buttons are likely to be swallowed by a child.

- Some of the noisy toy musical instruments have funky music such as rock and rap. Be sure to listen to musical toys, choose a quiet and uplifting one. Don't buy the annoying and loud one.

- Weapon toys are also not recommended. It's hard to say that their warlike voice and a set of bullets will have a positive effect on the child.

- Barbie dolls. These young female dolls in slim, stylish, make-up and revealing dresses are suitable for school-aged girls, but not for children. Because they also have body parts unfamiliar to the child.

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